

Classification with Multiple Generative Adversaries

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Abstract

In this work, we consider a natural extension of the two-player adversarial framework proposed by Goodfellow et al. [GPAM⁺14]; specifically, in our setting a single discriminative network will compete against multiple generative networks, with each attempting to produce realistic samples from one of N distinct distributions. The objective of the Discriminator will be to classify every given input to one of $2N$ categories: N real classes and their fake counterparts. As a result, our adversarial paradigm is explicitly formulated in order to train the Discriminator to perform classification. We provide a theoretical analysis of our proposed architecture, deriving an expression for the optimal Discriminator and investigating the best response from the Generators - under optimal play. Moreover, through experimental results in MNIST [LC10] we illustrate that our training method obtains strong performance with very limited training samples, outperforming the standard scheme for training Convolutional Neural Networks. Our empirical findings show that our model offers a compelling approach to prevent overfitting and circumscribe the generalization error, while at the same time the generative networks are able to produce samples with high perceptual score. The main caveat of our approach lies on the challenges of training in parallel multiple and competing neural networks.

Keywords: Classification; Generative Models; Data Augmentation; Regularization

1 Introduction

Generative models attempt to capture and simulate high-dimensional distributions - such as images and speech - and have attracted considerable attention due to their wide applicability. In this paper we emphasize on *Generative Adversarial Networks* (GANs) [GPAM⁺14], an adversarial framework for generating samples by way of a two-player minimax game. More precisely, given a data distribution p_{real} we train a Discriminator network $D(\mathbf{x}; \theta_d)$ to distinguish between real samples and samples artificially generated by the generator $G(\mathbf{z}; \theta_g) \sim p_g$. The objective of the Generator is to fool the Discriminator by transforming a latent vector \mathbf{z} drawn from a prior noise distribution p_z into synthetic data that are indistinguishable from the samples drawn from p_{real} . This generative paradigm has been employed in a wide line of research such as video generation [VPT16], domain transfer [YKP⁺16], high resolution image synthesis [WLZ⁺17], Cryptography [AA16] and Inference [DBP⁺16].

Moreover, GANs have been used for image classification tasks using semi-supervised learning - where only a small number of samples has been labelled - and have obtained state of the art

results in several tasks, outperforming standard techniques for training Convolutional Neural Networks. For a survey in semi-supervised learning with GANs we refer to the following [MO14, Gau15, Spr15, Ode16, SGZ⁺16]. In our work, we introduce a novel adversarial framework in which the Discriminator is explicitly trained as a classifier, optimizing its ability to distinguish between the different classes. The main intuition for our proposed architecture is that a single network will provide feedback to each Generator that attempts to produce samples from a single class; hence, it will gradually learn the important features and nuances that characterize each class. Indeed, one of our goals is to explore the duality between generation and classification: a neural network that understands how to generate samples from every class will be able to perform well on the task of classification.

Another significant parameter lies on the massive and very costly processing and analysis required in deep learning applications in order to collect and label the data. In fact, in several crucial environments - e.g. Medicine and Neurobiology - the available and reliable data are very limited. These restrictions have motivated the development of methods for augmenting the diversity of the available data, without actually collecting new samples. These techniques vary from very simple transformations, such as cropping or rotating the images in the dataset, to very sophisticated approaches where powerful generative models are employed to enhance the dataset. Recent work has shown that a very effective technique for enriching the dataset is based on GANs, [YKE19, dSTA19, MRS19]. Our approach lies on this line of research, attempting to enhance the dataset through generative methods. We additionally refer to [PW17] for multiple data augmentation solutions and heuristics in deep learning.

Finally, the research community in deep learning has invested substantial attention to develop efficient regularization techniques and models; essentially, generalization refers to how well a model can perform on unseen examples. Every model endeavors to minimize the generalization error and prevent over-adjusting its parameters on the training examples, a phenomenon known as overfitting. We refer to [KGC17] for a taxonomy on regularization methods and practical recommendations in deep learning and the work of Zhang et al. [ZBH⁺16] for a comprehensive study of generalization. Through this prism, we will illustrate that our architecture can act as an implicit regularizer, preventing overfitting.

Despite the remarkable success of GANs, they are notoriously hard to train. Indeed, guaranteeing convergence in minimax optimization problems requires training simultaneously multiple and competing neural networks, a task that requires a considerable amount of effort compared to traditional minimization problems with a single neural network. As a result, many empirical techniques and heuristics have been proposed (e.g. see [SGZ⁺16]) - and applied widely in practise - in order to increase the stability of the training process. In addition, more tractable theoretical formulations have been presented, such as Energy-based GANs [ZML16] and Variational Divergence Minimization [NCT16]. In this context, one of the main impediments of our model lies on the training overhead required to train multiple adversarial neural networks, even though the task of classification only requires a single neural network; essentially, the Generators will be only employed to train the classifier. Nonetheless, we will illustrate in our experiments that we are able in addition to produce realistic samples from each class; hence, our framework supplements the various models that have been proposed for generating labeled

samples, the most famous of which are the Conditional GANs [MO14].

The organization of this work consists of the following parts. First, we emphasize on the related work in the literature and we highlight our own contributions in Section 2. Next, we present some preliminaries on GANs in Section 3, before formally introducing our adversarial framework in 4.1 and our theoretical results in 4.2. In Section 5 we present our experimental results in MNIST, while we finally we conclude with remarks on our key contributions and potential future work Section 6.

2 Related Work

There has been extensive work on extending the adversarial framework proposed by Goodfellow et al. [GPAM⁺14] beyond the two-player game setting. One architectural proposition was to incorporate multiple Discriminators [DGM16]; this approach led to more reliable and stable training, as well as higher quality image samples. Moreover, schemes with multiple Generators and a single Discriminator - as our proposed model - have also received attention from the community. In the work of Ghosh et al. [GKN⁺17] the Discriminator - apart from identifying the fake samples - had to determine the generative network that actually produced the sample. In this way, the authors were able to tackle effectively the well-known empirical challenge of mode collapse and generate samples with higher variance, compared to the vanilla two-player framework. A different, game-theoretic approach [AGL⁺17] illustrated that it is computationally tractable to reach to an approximate Nash equilibrium using a mixture of generative networks; essentially, the Generator employs *mixed* strategies over a 'small' number of generative models, instead of using *pure* strategies, as in the original framework. Therefore, this approach improved the stability in the training phase.

Our work follows a similar path, in that it consists of multiple generative networks competing against a single Discriminator; however, we differentiate on some key points. In particular, in our model each Generator attempts to produce samples from a single and separate class or distribution, while the Discriminator has to accurately identify whether the input data are fake and their corresponding label; thus, we explicitly design the Discriminator as a classifier.

Finally, we should mention that there has been an extensive amount of work on establishing robust architectures and effective hierarchies of feature representation for training GANs. The architecture of our generative models is mainly based on the seminal paper on Deep Convolutional GANs [RMC15].

Contributions We provide a theoretical and empirical study of a very natural generalization of the two-player GAN framework. First, we derive the optimal Discriminator (Proposition 4.1), showing that the maximum-likelihood rule that was established in the original paper [GPAM⁺14] extends in our settings as well. On the other hand, the best response for each Generator involves - in general - a cross term, introducing impediments in the stability of our system. Importantly, our main contributions lie on our experimental findings; specifically, we train our model in MNIST and we establish the following key properties.

- Strong classification performance - through Data Augmentation - with very limited train-

ing samples, outperforming the standard training schemes in Convolutional Neural Networks (Table 1). It is important to point out our results apply without the use of pre-training or transfer learning techniques.

- Our model acts as an implicit regularizer, restraining the generalization error; indeed, we observed a remarkable difference in the learning curves of our model and the traditional training of a Convolutional Neural Network (Figure 2).
- Our generative networks are able to produce samples with high perceptual score (Figure 3).
- An ensemble of models boosts the performance; this property supplements the findings of Salimans et. al [SGZ⁺16] and corroborates with an observed property of GANs: the learning features in each training instance are slightly different.

Finally, we believe that our work could be of independent interest in a game-theoretic framework, in the context of graphical games [DB10].

3 Preliminaries

In this section, we present a brief review of Generative Adversarial Networks. Let $G(\mathbf{z}; \theta_g) : \mathbf{z} \mapsto \Phi$ and $D(\mathbf{x}; \theta_d) : \Phi \ni \mathbf{x} \mapsto [0, 1]$ denote two neural networks - namely the Generator and the Discriminator - with θ_g, θ_d their respective parameters and Φ the feature space. Moreover, let p_z denote some noise prior and p_{data} the true data distribution. The overall dynamic of the game can be captured by the following minimax objective function.

$$\min_{\theta_g} \max_{\theta_d} V(\theta_d, \theta_g) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_{data}} [\log D(\mathbf{x}; \theta_d)] + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z} \sim p_z} [\log(1 - D(G(\mathbf{z}; \theta_g); \theta_d))] \quad (1)$$

Essentially, the Discriminator attempts to maximize its ability to output a low probability whenever it receives as input synthetic data, and a high probability whenever it receives samples from the real distribution. On the other hand, the Generator has the exact opposite goal: produce realistic samples in order to fool the Generator. In the original theoretical analysis [GPAM⁺14], the game reaches an equilibrium when the Generator produces real samples $G(\mathbf{z}; \theta_g) \sim p_{data}$ and the Discriminator cannot differentiate between the two distributions, i.e. $D(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2}$.

4 Multi-Adversarial Architecture

4.1 Model

Consider a latent vector $\mathbf{z} \sim p_z$ - where p_z denotes the noise distribution¹ and N separate classes, with each class n represented with probability density function p_n residing in some common feature space Φ . Through this prism, we will employ N distinct neural networks $G_n(\mathbf{z}; \theta_n^g)$, where θ_n^g are the parameters of the corresponding Generator. The goal of each Generator n will be to construct realistic samples from class p_n . On the other hand, a single discriminator $D(\mathbf{x}; \theta^d)$

¹A multivariate Gaussian prior is commonly used in practise

will receive some vector $\mathbf{x} \in \Phi$ and will have to determine its class. In our setting, we consider $2N$ separate classes: N real classes and their artificial counterparts. To be precise, the Discriminator will map every input vector \mathbf{x} to a probability vector $[\mathbf{r}^T \mid \mathbf{f}^T]^T = [r_1, \dots, r_N, f_1, \dots, f_N]^T$, where the term $r_j = r_j(\mathbf{x})$ corresponds to the real classes j , whilst the term $f_j = f_j(\mathbf{x})$ to the fake class j . Therefore, if $\phi : [0, 1] \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ denotes a monotone and concave *measuring function*, the dynamic of the game can be described as follows.

1. Fix the Generators $\Gamma = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_N\}$; then, the Discriminator endeavors to maximize its ability to accurately classify every input to one of the $2N$ classes by maximizing the following virtual criterion.

$$V(D; \Gamma) = \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim p_n(\mathbf{x})} [\phi(r_n(\mathbf{x}))] + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z} \sim p_z(\mathbf{z})} [\phi(f_n(G_n(\mathbf{z})))] \right) \quad (2)$$

2. Fix the Discriminator D . One possible objective for the Generators would be to minimize the utility of the Discriminator; however, this utility model can eventually lead to vanishing gradients, as observed in [GPAM⁺14]. Note that each Generator can directly influence a single component on the summation (2), namely the term that indicates whether it has succeeded in fooling the discriminator. Thus, we define the following utility for the Generators.

$$V(G_n; D) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{z} \sim p_z(\mathbf{z})} [\phi(r_n(G_n(\mathbf{z})))], \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (3)$$

It is worth mentioning that for a single class $N = 1$ and $\phi(x) = \log x$ the aforementioned formulation coincides with GAN objective that is used in practice; in this sense, our architecture generalizes the two-player game setting. For the theoretical analysis 4.2 we will assume that $\phi(x) = \log x$, while in our experiments we will employ an appropriate variation that has shown to ameliorate the stability of the learning process based on the *Wasserstein* distance metric [ACB17], where $\phi(x) = x$.

The main purpose of our architecture is to train the Discriminator as a classifier; through this prism, the main question is how to employ the output of the Discriminator in order to classify every given input $\mathbf{x} \in \Phi$. Perhaps the most natural answer is to construe $p(\mathbf{x}) = r_n(\mathbf{x}) + f_n(\mathbf{x})$ as the posterior probability of class n . Therefore, our prediction rule will derive from the Maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimation, which implies that

$$\text{prediction} = \arg \max_{n=1, \dots, N} \{r_n(\mathbf{x}) + f_n(\mathbf{x})\} \quad (4)$$

4.2 Theoretical Analysis

In this section, we derive an expression for the optimal Discriminator and through this result we investigate the state of equilibrium in our system. First, we state an auxiliary lemma that will be applied to derive the best response for the Discriminator.

Figure 1: Every Generator G_n attempts to produce synthetic data - through the transformation of a latent vector \mathbf{z} - in order to fool the Discriminator, that is activate the output neuron r_n . The last layer of the Discriminator is a softmax activation function, so that the outputs can be interpreted as posterior probabilities.

Lemma 4.1. Let $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) \in \mathbb{R}^k \setminus \{\mathbf{0}\}$ with $a_i \geq 0, \forall i$ and $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, \dots, p_k)$ a probability vector; then, function $g : \mathbf{p} \mapsto \sum_{i=1}^k a_i \log p_i$ achieves its maximum for $p_i = a_i / \sum_{i=1}^k a_i$.

Proof. Let $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ a probability vector with $q_i = a_i / \sum_{i=1}^k a_i$; then, it follows that

$$g(\mathbf{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^k a_i \log p_i = \left(\sum_{i=1}^k a_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^k q_i \log p_i \right) \quad (5)$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=1}^k a_i \right) \left(\sum_{i=1}^k q_i \log \frac{p_i}{q_i} + \sum_{i=1}^k q_i \log q_i \right) \quad (6)$$

$$= - \left(\sum_{i=1}^k a_i \right) (KL(\mathbf{q} \parallel \mathbf{p}) + H(\mathbf{q})) \quad (7)$$

As a result, the maximization of g is tantamount to the minimization of $KL(\mathbf{q} \parallel \mathbf{p})$ and hence, the maximum is obtained if and only if $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{q}$. □

Proposition 4.1. For a fixed set of Generators $\Gamma = \{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_N\}$ and input \mathbf{x} , the optimal discriminator D^* can be described as follows

$$r_n^*(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{p_n(\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (p_i(\mathbf{x}) + g_i(\mathbf{x}))} \quad (8)$$

$$f_n^*(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{g_n(\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (p_i(\mathbf{x}) + g_i(\mathbf{x}))} \quad (9)$$

Proof. For any set of Generators Γ , the discriminator D attempts to maximize

$$\begin{aligned}
V(D; \Gamma) &= \sum_{n=1}^N \left(\int_{\mathbf{x}} [p_n(\mathbf{x}) \log r_n(\mathbf{x}) + g_n(\mathbf{x}) \log f_n(\mathbf{x})] d\mathbf{x} \right) \\
&= \int_{\mathbf{x}} \left(\sum_{n=1}^N [p_n(\mathbf{x}) \log r_n(\mathbf{x}) + g_n(\mathbf{x}) \log f_n(\mathbf{x})] \right) d\mathbf{x}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

It is clear that the Discriminator can remain undefined for every \mathbf{x} such that $p_n(\mathbf{x}) = g_n(\mathbf{x}) = 0, \forall n = 1, 2, \dots, N$; indeed, the utility of the Discriminator does not depend on its behavior in these regions. Hence, we can apply Lemma 4.1 in order to conclude the proof. \square

For notational simplicity, let $\bar{p} = (p_1 + \dots + p_N)/N$ and $\bar{g} = (g_1 + \dots + g_N)/N$; assuming that the Discriminator responds optimally, the utility function for each Generator G_n can be reformulated as

$$\begin{aligned}
V(G_n; D^*) &= \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{x} \sim g_n(\mathbf{x})} \left[\log \frac{p_n(\mathbf{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (p_i(\mathbf{x}) + g_i(\mathbf{x}))} \right] \\
&= -\log 2N - KL(g_n \parallel p_n) + \underbrace{KL\left(g_n \parallel \frac{\bar{p} + \bar{g}}{2}\right)}_{\text{Cross Term}}
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

As a result, the state of equilibrium does not necessarily occur when $g_n = p_n, \forall n$. Indeed, although replicating the actual distribution maximizes the second term in the virtual criterion (11), the cross term depends on the action space of the other Generators and the entirety of the real distributions; thus, the cross term complicates the dynamics of the game and could introduce undesirable interference between the optimization of the Generators. Nonetheless, in our experimental section we shall establish that each generative model learns to approximate the real distribution - producing realistic samples - and consequently, the distinguishing ability of the Discriminator improves by encountering artificial samples that resemble the actual classes.

5 Experiments

In order to illustrate the strong properties of our model, we evaluated our model in MNIST [LC10]. Specifically, we first trained our networks with 32 and 64 training samples from each class, employing batches of 32 samples; for the validation we used a single batch. Our results are presented in Table 1. It is important to stress that the performance of any model with restricted training set can be widely improved with the use of transfer learning and pre-training techniques - in the case of MNIST even with a single sample per class; nonetheless, our results apply without employing such techniques and optimizing solely on the given training samples.

Moreover, our model manages to prevent overfitting, acting as an implicit regularizer, as illustrated in Figure 2; indeed, the learning curves of our model are in stark contrast with those of a traditional Convolutional Neural Network that is susceptible to overfitting, especially when

a limited number of training samples is available. Finally, the generative networks in our model were able to perceptually approximate the desirable distributions (Figure 3), a property which is crucial in order to improve the distinguishing ability of the Discriminator.

A rather surprising property of the dynamics in our adversarial framework is that the evolution of the training losses of the Generators is relatively balanced - without introducing any empirical controlling mechanism. We also observed that normalizing the utility of the Discriminator (2) - by dividing by N - is crucial to balance the progress between the Discriminator and the Generators. For all our experiments we used learning rate $\eta = 4 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

Table 1: The performance obtained from different models. We denote with k Ens Cl -GAN an ensemble of k of our models, where the prediction is derived through the mechanism of *hard voting*. To make the comparison meaningful, the Discriminator and the CNN have the same architecture. We remark that these results are the average over multiple simulations.

	32 Samples per Class	64 Samples per Class
CNN	84.88%	90.21%
Cl -GAN	90.38%	94.38%
3Ens Cl -GAN	91.76%	95.23%
5Ens Cl -GAN	92.23%	95.54%

Figure 2: The learning curves of our model (rightmost image) and a CNN (leftmost image) with the same architecture as the Discriminator. The x-axis represents the number of epochs, while y-axis the accuracy of the model; in particular, the orange color corresponds to the accuracy in the validation set and cobalt to the accuracy in the training set. These results have been obtained with 5 batches of training samples. Note that although the learning curves correspond to the same neural network, the training dynamics are inherently different; specifically, our model exhibits very limited generalization error - managing to substantially combat overfitting, yet requiring more training cycles and resources to stabilize.

Table 2: The architecture of each Generator; the convolutional layers are implied to be transposed (or *Deconvolutional*). We should also point out that the input of each Generator is a 3-dimensional latent vector, sampled by a multivariate Gaussian distribution.

Layer	Filters	Kernel Size	Stride	Batch-Norm	Activation
Fully Connected	1	-	-	Yes	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	256	4×4	1	Yes	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	128	4×4	2	Yes	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	8	5×5	2	Yes	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	1	4×4	1	Yes	tanh

Table 3: The architecture of the Discriminator. The input of the first layer is a 28×28 gray-scale image, with the value of every pixel normalized in $[-1, 1]$. Note that every convolutional layer employs Dropout with probability $p = 0.3$.

Layer	Filters	Kernel Size	Stride	Batch-Norm	Activation
Convolutional	8	4×4	1	No	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	64	4×4	1	No	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	128	5×5	1	No	Leaky-ReLU
Convolutional	256	4×4	1	No	Leaky-ReLU
Fully Connected	1	-	-	No	softmax

Figure 3: Exemplar samples produced by our generative models (leftmost image) and random samples from MNIST (rightmost image); as a result, we were able to train simultaneously 10 Generators that produce samples with high perceptual score with only a single Discriminator. We should mention that these examples have been selected from different stages of the training phase.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, we have introduced a novel adversarial framework that is explicitly defined in order to perform classification. Through empirical evaluation, we illustrated several desirable properties of our classifier, including effective Data Augmentation and regularization. An interesting avenue for future research would be to reinforce parameter sharing between the Generators - as in [GKN⁺17], in order to reduce redundant computations and improve the stability of the system; intuitively, the Generators would implicitly cooperate, with the more advanced networks assisting the slow learners. Another interesting approach to accelerate the stability would be to employ a different utility function - potentially a dynamic one - for the Discriminator, instead of using a uniform summation over the losses in each individual game. For instance, introducing weights in the utility function could lead to more balanced evolution in the dynamics. Finally, our work motivates the study of more sophisticated adversarial architectures in the context of GANs.

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